

**METHODOLOGICAL ISSUES OF ASSESSING
ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY IN AGRICULTURE****Umaraliyev Olimjon Raushanovich****Gulistan State University****Senior Lecturer, Department of Economics****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19598135>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 10th April 2026Accepted: 12th April 2026Online: 14th April 2026**KEYWORDS**

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ABSTRACT

This article provides an in-depth analysis of methodological issues in assessing economic efficiency in agriculture. In particular, the main indicators used to determine production efficiency in the agricultural sector, methods for calculating them, and assessment criteria are highlighted. Also, the theoretical and methodological aspects of determining the efficiency of using land, labor, capital, and material resources are considered. The article substantiates the importance of using modern economic analysis methods in assessing economic efficiency in agricultural enterprises and systematically analyzes the factors affecting efficiency. The results of the study are of significant scientific and practical importance in making management decisions, rational use of resources, and increasing competitiveness in the agricultural sector.

Introduction. The agricultural sector is of strategic importance in the country's economy, playing an important role in providing the population with food products, ensuring the uninterrupted supply of raw materials to industrial sectors, and increasing export potential. Especially in a market economy, the sustainable development of the agricultural sector largely depends on its level of economic efficiency. Therefore, the correct assessment of economic efficiency in agriculture, the improvement of its methodological foundations and its implementation in practice are considered to be one of the urgent scientific issues. Agriculture differs from other sectors in its natural and economic characteristics. In particular, the seasonality of the production process, the participation of land resources as the main means of production, the strong influence of natural and climatic factors, and the relatively long period of product cultivation require a special approach to methods for assessing efficiency in this sector. These factors create the need to use methodological mechanisms that take into account the specifics of the sector, in addition to traditional methods, when determining economic efficiency indicators.

In the current environment, rational use of resources in agriculture, reduction of production costs, increase in the volume and quality of products, and increase in the level of profitability are emerging as important criteria for assessing economic efficiency. In this context, scientific research on methodological issues of efficiency assessment is of not only theoretical but also practical importance.

Analysis and results. The issue of assessing economic efficiency in agriculture is one of the most important scientific areas of agrarian economics. Determining efficiency in this sector requires not only measuring the volume of production, but also a comprehensive analysis of the level of use of available resources, cost efficiency, and final financial results. In this regard, methodological approaches to assessing economic efficiency are formed on the basis of multifactor analysis.

First of all, in assessing economic efficiency in agriculture, productivity, labor productivity, cost of production, profit and profitability are of particular importance. Scientific sources emphasize that increasing productivity has a direct positive effect on economic efficiency. In particular, recently published statistical analyses have proven that increasing productivity serves to increase the volume of gross output, reduce costs per unit of output, and increase farm income.

The analysis shows that it is not enough to limit oneself to absolute indicators when assessing economic efficiency. For example, the volume of gross product may be high, but if this result is achieved at the expense of excessive resource consumption or high costs, then the actual economic efficiency will be low. Therefore, relative indicators, especially the level of profitability, are used as an important methodological criterion.

Profitability is assessed based on the following classical formula:

$$R = \frac{F}{X} \times 100\%$$

Here:

R – profitability ratio,

F – net profit,

X – total expenses.

This indicator expresses how much profit an agricultural enterprise receives for the funds spent. In scientific research, this indicator is widely used as one of the main criteria for assessing efficiency.

In addition, in modern methodological approaches, the use of production functions in assessing economic efficiency is expanding. In particular, in a study conducted on the example of farms in the Samarkand region, technical efficiency was assessed based on the Cobb-Douglas production function and the Tobit regression model. According to the results, the average technical efficiency indicator was determined at 0.868, which indicates that the efficiency of using existing resources is high, but there is still room for additional growth.

This result is methodologically very important, since it shows the need to assess economic efficiency not only through financial results, but also based on the optimal combination of resources. That is, the ratios between land area, labor resources, machinery, seed and fertilizer consumption have a significant impact on efficiency. The analysis also highlighted the issue of introducing innovative technologies as another important factor. Recent studies have shown that the introduction of modern technologies into the processing of agricultural products can reduce costs, improve product quality, and expand export potential. This is recognized as an important factor leading to increased economic efficiency.

The results show that methodological issues of assessing economic efficiency in agriculture require a multifaceted approach. On the one hand, traditional indicators - productivity, profit, cost and profitability - are important, on the other hand, it is necessary to

take into account econometric models, statistical regression methods and innovative factors. As a general conclusion, it can be said that a comprehensive methodological approach based on a system of indicators is the most optimal for assessing economic efficiency in agriculture. This approach allows for a deep analysis of the real economic situation of agricultural enterprises, effective management decisions and increased efficiency in resource use.

Table 1
Main indicators of economic efficiency assessment in agriculture and their analytical description

Nº	Indicator name	Calculation method	Economic content	Analytical significance
1	Productivity	Gross product/land area (ha)	It represents the volume of output from one hectare.	Evaluates the efficiency of land resource use
2	Labor productivity	Gross product / number of employees	Product volume per employee	Shows the efficiency of using labor resources
3	Product cost	Total cost / product volume	Indicates the cost of producing one unit of product	Evaluates the level of cost optimization
4	Net profit	Total revenue – total cost	Represents the final financial result of the enterprise	Determines the economic effectiveness of the activity
5	Profitability ratio	(Net profit / total cost) × 100%	Profit ratio relative to costs	Key indicator of financial performance
6	Capital Blue	Gross product/value of fixed assets	Efficiency of fixed capital use	Evaluates investment performance
7	Resource efficiency	Product size / total resources	Result in relation to resources spent	The complex represents economic efficiency

The table data clearly shows that the process of assessing economic efficiency in agriculture is based on a system of multifactor indicators. These indicators are closely related to each other and comprehensively reflect various aspects of the production process. First of all, the productivity indicator is one of the most important criteria for determining economic efficiency in the agricultural sector. This indicator expresses the volume of output obtained from one hectare of land and allows us to assess the level of use of land resources. An increase in productivity, as a rule, serves to increase overall economic efficiency through an increase in the volume of output and a decrease in fixed costs per unit of output. At the same time, the labor productivity indicator also plays an important role in analyzing the efficiency of agricultural enterprises. This indicator expresses the volume of output per employee and

helps to determine the efficiency of using labor resources. High labor productivity indicates that technological approaches to the production process are correctly implemented, the level of qualification and organization of the workforce is sufficient.

The product cost indicator shown in the table highlights the financial aspect of assessing economic efficiency. This indicator, which represents the total costs incurred for the production of one unit of product, is an important methodological tool for determining the level of cost optimization. If the cost of the product decreases, the enterprise's ability to make a profit increases, which directly affects the increase in the level of profitability.

The net profit indicator represents the final economic result of the enterprise's activities and is formed as the difference between total revenue and total costs. This indicator is considered one of the main criteria for assessing the financial stability and economic condition of the enterprise. An increase in the amount of net profit indicates the effective organization of the production process and the rational use of resources.

The level of profitability stands out as the most important relative indicator in assessing economic efficiency. This indicator expresses the share of profit received in relation to costs in percentage terms, showing how effectively the funds spent are used. It is profitability that is important for a deep analysis of the economic efficiency of the enterprise and for making management decisions.

In addition, the indicators of return on capital and resource efficiency are important components of modern economic analysis. While return on capital expresses the efficiency of using fixed assets, resource efficiency comprehensively reflects the impact of all resources spent in the production process on the final result. This indicates the need to apply a systematic approach to assessing economic efficiency in agriculture, not limited to just one indicator.

In general, the data in the table confirm that the assessment of economic efficiency in agriculture should be carried out on the basis of an interrelated system of indicators. Such an approach allows for a full reflection of the real state of the production process, identification of existing problems and development of scientific and practical proposals for increasing efficiency.

Conclusions and suggestions. According to the results of this study, it was found that the methodological issues of assessing economic efficiency in agriculture are complex and multifactorial. The correct assessment of efficiency in the agricultural sector is directly dependent not only on the volume of production and final financial results, but also on the level of resource utilization, the efficiency of technological processes and the quality of the management system. Therefore, in assessing economic efficiency, along with traditional indicators - productivity, labor productivity, product cost, net profit and profitability, the use of modern econometric approaches and production functions is of great scientific and practical importance.

The analysis shows that the efficiency of land, labor, capital and material resources is inextricably linked, and their optimal use is the main factor in achieving high economic results. At the same time, the introduction of innovative technologies serves to reduce production costs, increase product quality and improve profitability. Therefore, increasing economic efficiency in agriculture requires a comprehensive and systematic approach in many respects.

In this regard, it is advisable to implement a number of proposals to further increase economic efficiency in agricultural enterprises. In particular, it is necessary to improve the efficiency assessment system and establish a comprehensive analysis of indicators in it, widely use econometric models and modern statistical methods in assessing economic processes, as well as strengthen mechanisms for rational use of resources. In addition, the widespread introduction of innovative technologies in the agricultural sector, digitization of production processes and modernization of the management system should be considered as important areas for increasing economic efficiency. At the same time, improving the skills of sector employees and establishing a continuous monitoring system will also serve to sustainably improve production efficiency. In general, systematic approaches aimed at assessing and increasing economic efficiency in agriculture are an important factor in strengthening the competitiveness of the agricultural sector, efficient use of resources, and ensuring sustainable economic development.

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